

О. А. Коваленко та ін. *Пластична, реконструктивна і естетична хірургія*. 2018. № 1-2. С. 48-61.

6. Місце ліпофілінгу в комплексному лікуванні хворих на рак грудної залози: історичні аспекти та власний досвід / І. І. Смолянко та ін. *Клиническая онкология*. 2015. Т. 19, № 3. С. 40-44.

7. Мяделец О. Д., Соболевская И. С., Мяделец В. О. Гистофизиология жиросодержащих структур кожи: пособие. Витебск: ВГМУ, 2015. 291 с.

8. Слесаренко С. В., Баранов І. В., Ноп Н. М., Циганков К. В. Реорганізація тканинної структури рубців шкіри при застосуванні ліпофілінгу. *Пластична, реконструктивна і естетична хірургія*. 2019. № 3-4. С. 22-31.

9. Brewin M. P., Homer S. J. The lived experience and quality of life with burn scarring—the results from a large-scale online survey. *Burns*. 2018. Vol. 44. P. 1801-1810. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2018.04.007>

10. Endothelial differentiated adipose-derived stem cells improvement of survival and neovascularization in fat transplantation / W. M. Harris et al. *Aesthetic surgery journal*. 2018. Vol. 39, No. 2. P. 220-232. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjy130>

11. Gal S., Ramirez J. I., Maguina P. Autologous fat grafting does not improve burn scar appearance: a prospective, randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled, pilot study. *Burns*. 2017. Vol. 43, No. 3. P. 486-489. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2016.09.019>

12. Lipofilling influence on the tissue structure of the skin scars / P. Badiul et al. *European Journal Burn Care*. 2020. No. 1. P. 150.

13. Roger K., Khouri, Jr. Roger, Khouri K. Current Clinical Applications of Fat Grafting. *Plastic Reconstructive Surgery*. 2017. No. 3. P. 466-486. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0000000000003648>

14. Seo B. F., Jung S. N. The immunomodulatory effects of mesenchymal stem cells in prevention or treatment of excessive scars. *Stem cells international*. 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/6937976>

15. Studies in fat grafting: Part IV. Adipose-derived stromal cell gene expression in cell-assisted lipotransfer / R. M. Garza et al. *Plastic Reconstructive Surgery*. 2015. No. 135. P. 1045-1055. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0000000000001104>

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MICROBIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF SPUTUM IN STABLE ADULT PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIECTASIS IN THE DNIPRO REGION OF UKRAINE

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Ключевые слова: бронхоэктазия, бронхоэктазы, мокрота, антибиотикорезистентность, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Abstract. Microbiological profile of sputum in stable adult patients with bronchiectasis in the Dnipro region of Ukraine. Gashynova K.Yu., Suska K.S., Dmytrychenko V.V. *Chronic respiratory tract infection and relapsing exacerbations worsen the quality and reduce the life expectancy of patients with bronchiectasis. This work aimed to identify the spectrum of pathogens and to determine their profile of antibiotic resistance in the sputum of patients with bronchiectasis in the Dnipro region. Sputum of 60 patients in a stable phase with confirmed bronchiectasis was a subject to microbiological examination and determination of antibiotic sensitivity according to generally accepted CLSI recommendations. According to the results of the study, it was found that 70% of patients have sputum colonization by pathogens in the stable phase of the disease, and the most common pathogens are Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Haemophilus influenzae, which is in line with the global trend. Haemophilus influenzae was sensitive to ampicillin, amoxicillin, amoxicillin/clavulanate, piperacillin/tazobactam, cefuroxime, ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, cefepime, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin and moxifloxacin in a hundred percent of cases. However, more than half of the strains of Pseudomonas aeruginosa were resistant to one or more drugs with anti-Pseudomonas activity. In particular, the highest level of resistance was identified to such drugs as imipenem, aztreonam, ceftazidime. The problem of antibiotic resistance is alarming and once again indicates the need for the regular microbiological examination of the sputum of patients with bronchiectasis even in a stable phase for subsequent rational administration of antibacterial therapy.*

Реферат. Микробиологический профиль мокроты у стабильных взрослых больных бронхоэктазией в Днепровском регионе Украины. Гашинова К.Ю., Суська К.С., Дмитриченко В.В. *Хроническая инфекция дыхательных путей и рецидивирующие обострения ухудшают качество и снижают продолжительность жизни пациентов с бронхоэктазией. Целью данной работы было выявление спектра патогенов и определение их профиля антибиотикорезистентности в мокроте пациентов с бронхоэктазией Днепровского региона. Мокрота 60 пациентов в стабильной фазе с подтвержденной бронхоэктазией подлежала микробиологическому исследованию и определению антибиотикочувствительности согласно общепринятым рекомендациям CLSI. По результатам исследования установлено, что 70% пациентов имеют колонизацию мокроты патогенными возбудителями в стабильной фазе заболевания, а наиболее частыми возбудителями являются Pseudomonas aeruginosa и Haemophilus influenzae, что соответствует мировой тенденции. Haemophilus influenzae была чувствительна к препаратам ампициллин, амоксициллин, амоксициллин/клавуланат, пиперациллин/тазобактам, цефуроксим, цефтриаксон, цефотаксим, цефепим, ципрофлоксацин, левофлоксацин и моксифлоксацин в ста процентах случаев. Однако более половины штаммов Pseudomonas aeruginosa оказались резистентными к одному и более препаратам с антисинегнойной активностью, в частности, самый высокий уровень резистентности выявлен к препаратам имипенем, азтреонам, цефтазидим. Проблема антибиотикорезистентности настораживает и в очередной раз указывает на необходимость регулярного микробиологического исследования мокроты пациентов с бронхоэктазией даже в стабильной фазе с целью последующего рационального назначения антибактериальной терапии.*

Bronchiectasis (BE) is a chronic respiratory disease characterized by clinical cough syndrome, sputum production, chronic respiratory infection and radiologically abnormal permanent bronchodilation [11]. The prevalence of BE in Europe and North America ranges from 67 to 566 per 100,000 population, while in China it is 1,200 per 100,000. Chronic respiratory infection, inflammation and exacerbation are the main components of the alteration vicious circle which leads to damage to the bronchial walls and lung tissue [12]. Neutrophilic inflammation occupies a key position in the body's immune response to infection; in turn, neutrophil proteases lead to further damage to the tissues of the respiratory tract and trigger a cascade of pathophysiological reactions [11]. One of the main challenges for scientists and clinicians is the identification of etiological factors in the development of BE which is associated with the heterogeneity of various aspects of the disease [10]. From a clinical point of view, the classic patient with BE suffers from daily productive cough with

periodic exacerbations, but there is a population of patients in whom BE can be detected accidentally during the examination for pneumonia or hemoptysis. In turn, some patients may have an almost asymptomatic course of the disease. From a functional point of view, patients can have both normal external respiratory function and obstructive or restrictive disorders [8].

Exacerbations of BE is a key target for therapy as they are associated with increased severity of local and systemic inflammation and progressive lung damage [16]. Limited data indicate that during exacerbations patients with BE often secrete those bacterial species that usually colonize sputum in a stable phase [4]. Detection of the pathogen during exacerbation may be a consequence of bacterial growth of a pre-existing microorganism, and may be associated with gaining of new strains [15]. Existing recommendations for the management of BE patients suggest to study the culture of sputum at least once a year in a stable phase [11].

Pseudomonas aeruginosa and *Haemophilus influenzae* are now the most common bacteria found in the sputum and broncho-alveolar lavage of patients with BE, but other pathogens, including fungi, mycobacteria and viruses can also colonize the airways of patients [12]. It is known that the microbiological profile of sputum and the sensitivity of the detected pathogens to antibiotics in BE patients depends on many factors, including geographical location [12]. At the same time, there are only isolated data on the state of this problem in Ukraine [2, 3, 14].

The aim of the work is to study the microbiological profile of sputum of BE patients in the stable phase and the profile of antibiotic resistance in the Dnipro region of Ukraine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

Patients with BE (residents of Dnipropetrovsk region) were prospectively included in the study on the basis of the Department of Occupational Diseases and Clinical Immunology of the State Establishment "Dnipropetrovsk Medical Academy of Health Ministry of Ukraine" from October 2018 to October 2019. Inclusion criteria: adult men and women with BE confirmed by high-resolution computed tomography on the basis of the following radiographic criteria: 1) no bronchial narrowing in the direction from the center to the periphery; 2) the inner diameter of the bronchi is larger than the diameter of the corresponding pulmonary artery or 3) visualization of the peripheral bronchi with an interval of one centimeter from the surface of the visceral pleura [6]. The stable phase of BE (absence of change of symptoms and a therapeutic mode within at least 8 weeks) was obligatory. Exclusion criteria: cystic fibrosis, active tuberculosis, history of malignancy, pregnancy and lactation.

Sputum samples were considered suitable for evaluation if they contained <10 squamous epithelial cells in the field of view under microscopy. Microbiological examination of sputum samples was performed by conventional bacteriological methods of growth on nutrient media [9]. Sputum was obtained by the method of spontaneous expectoration, in patients with unproductive cough it was planned to study the induced sputum. Susceptibility to antibacterial drugs was determined using the disc-diffusion method according to standards [7, 13].

Statistical analysis was performed using STATISTICA 6.1 (StatSoft Inc., USA, N AGAR909 E415822FA). Data were presented as mean (standard deviation, SD) in the case of quantitative variables, or as absolute numbers and percentage (n,%) in the case of qualitative variables. The

distribution of variables was analyzed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The chi-square criterion was used to compare two independent binary samples. The 95% confidence interval was calculated for independent variables, with $p \leq 0.05$ being considered significant [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

60 patients with BE in a stable phase were included in the study. The average age of patients was 52.9 ± 14.3 years (from 23 to 74 years), 15 of them were men (25%). Patients mostly had no history of smoking – 46 patients (76.7%) never smoked. In 52 (86.7%) patients sputum was obtained during spontaneous expectoration. Pathogens were detected in the sputum of 43 patients (71.7%), eight of whom had a combination of pathogens (13.3%). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (n=15) was the most common, of which six were mucoid strains (40%) and *Haemophilus influenzae* (n=15). The results of isolation of pathogens are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Among the combinations of pathogens there were combinations of *Haemophilus influenzae* with *Candida albicans* (n=2), with *Escherichia coli* (n=1), with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (n=1) and with *Aspergillus* spp (n=1); combinations of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with *Haemophilus influenzae* (n=1), with *Aspergillus niger* (n=1); combination of *Escherichia coli* with *Candida albicans* (n=1).

Among 15 clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, seven (46.7%) were sensitive to such antibacterial drugs as ticarcillin/clavulanate, piperacillin/tazobactam, aztreonam, ceftazidime, cefepime, imipenem, meropenem, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, gentamicin, amikacin, tobramycin, three (20%) were resistant to one of the drugs (levofloxacin, gentamicin, imipenem) and five isolates (33.3%) were polyresistant. Among those with resistance, non-mucoid clinical isolates predominated – ix of the nine non-mucoid (66.7%) and two of the six mucoid (33.3%) were resistant to one or more antibacterial drugs, but statistically the difference was insignificant ($p=0.9$ by the criterion of chi-square). According to the data presented in Figure 3, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in this patient population was the most resistant to imipenem (33.3%), aztreonam (26.7%) and ceftazidime (26.7%). In turn, most clinical isolates were sensitive to ticarcillin/clavulanate (93.3%), piperacillin/tazobactam (93.3%) and levofloxacin (93.3%). Resistance to cefepime, meropenem, gentamicin and tobramycin was found in 20% of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates, and to ciprofloxacin and amikacin in 13.3%.

Fig. 1. Profile of microbiological pathogens revealed in sputum of patients with BE in a stable phase

Fig. 2. Qualitative findings of isolated microorganisms in patients with BE in a stable phase

Fig. 3. Resistance phenotype of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to antibacterial drugs

All clinical isolates of *Haemophilus influenzae* (n=15) were sensitive to such drugs as ampicillin, amoxicillin, amoxicillin/clavulanate, piperacillin/tazobactam, cefuroxin, ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, cefepime, ciprofloxacin, cyprofloxacin.

Among other pathogens resistance of two isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* (66.7%) and one isolate of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (50%) to drugs from the group of macrolides (erythromycin, azithromycin) and to clindamycin was revealed as well.

Among all clinical isolates that had resistance to at least one of the antibacterial drugs, only one isolate had a combination with another microorganism – polyresistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (mucoid strain) with *Aspergillus niger* (9.1%).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Almost 87% of patients in the stable phase of the disease produce sputum and in 70% of patients pathological pathogens are detected using bacteriological methods of sputum examination. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Haemophilus influenzae* prevailed.

2. There is a problem of polyresistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to antibacterial drugs, in particular, more than a quarter of strains were resistant to imipenem, aztreonam and ceftazidime.

At the same time, there was no statistically significant difference between the sensitivity to antibacterial drugs between mucoid and non-mucoid strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The presence of an additional pathogenicity factor, such as the mucoid phenotype, requires further study.

3. *Haemophilus influenzae* in this population of patients was present in one hundred percent of cases sensitive to penicillins and protected penicillins, cephalosporins of the second, third and fourth generations, fluoroquinolones of the second and third generations. In turn, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* have shown extremely high levels of resistance to macrolides and lincosamides, but the prevalence of these pathogens in this population is low, so further observations and studies are needed.

4. Based on the results obtained in BE patients in the Dnipro region, we consider it appropriate to monitor the microbiological profile of sputum of patients in a stable phase. And for the treatment of patients with frequent exacerbations, it is advisable to prescribe an antibiotic according to the resistance profile.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Antomonov MYu. [Mathematical processing and analysis of biomedical data]. 2-e izd. Kyiv: Medinform; 2018. p. 579. Russian. Available from: <https://www.olx.ua/.../antomonov-m-yu-monografya>.
2. Pertseva TO, Gashynova KYu, Dmytrychenko VV, et al. Bronchoectatic disease: the state of art and the clinical case. *Medicni perspektivi*. 2018;23(3):153-61. Ukrainian. doi: [https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2018.3\(part1\).142360](https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2018.3(part1).142360)
3. Feshchenko YI, Gavrisyuk VK, Dziublyk IV, Dziublyk OYa. [Infectious exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: place and role of respiratory viral pathogens.]. *Medicni perspektivi*. 2019;24(4):30-35. doi: <https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2019.4.189191>
4. Vidal OS, Perea L, Cantó E, et al. Antimicrobial peptides and airway bacterial colonization in bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J*. 2018;53(Suppl62):OA4948. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.congress-2018.OA4948>
5. Hill AT, Sullivan AL, Chalmers JD, et al. British Thoracic Society guideline for bronchiectasis in adults. *Thorax*. 2019;74(Suppl. 1):1-69. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2018-212463>
6. Diaz AA, Young TP, Maselli DJ, et al. Bronchoarterial ratio in never-smokers adults: implications for bronchial dilation definition. *Respirology*. 2017;22(1):108-13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/resp.12875>
7. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. CLSI M100 S27:2017. Performance standard for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. 27th edn. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute; 2017.
8. Radovanovic D, Santus P, Blasi F, et al. A comprehensive approach to lung function in bronchiectasis. *Respir Med* 2018;145:120-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2018.10.031>
9. Cornaglia G, Courcol R and Herrmann J-L. *European Manual of Clinical Microbiology*; 2012.
10. Lonni S, Chalmers JD, Goeminne PC, et al. Etiology of non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis in adults and its correlation to disease severity. *Ann Am Thorac Soc* 2015;12:1764-70. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201507-472OC>
11. Polverino E, Goeminne PC, McDonnell MJ, et al. European Respiratory Society guidelines for the management of adult bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J*. 2017;50:1700629. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00629-2017>
12. Chandrasekaran R, Mac Aogain M, Chalmers JD, Elborn SJ, Chotirmall SH. Geographic variation in the aetiology, epidemiology and microbiology of bronchiectasis. *Bmc Pulmonary Medicine*. 2018;18:14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-018-0638-0>
13. Matuschek E, Brown DFJ and Kahlmeter G. Development of the EUCAST disk diffusion antimicrobial susceptibility testing method and its implementation in routine microbiology laboratories. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2014;20:O255-66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-0691.12373>
14. Gashynova K, Suska K, Dmytrychenko V. Microbiome landscape and disease duration role in allergy in adult patients with bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J*. 2019;54(Suppl63):PA2763. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.congress-2019.PA2763>
15. Polverino E, Rosales-Mayor E, Benegas M. Pneumonic and non-pneumonic exacerbations in bronchiectasis: clinical and microbiological differences. *J Infect*. 2018;77:99-106. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2018.04.006>
16. Chalmers JD, Goeminne P, Aliberti S, et al. The bronchiectasis severity index. An international derivation and validation study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2014;189:576-85. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201309-1575OC>

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Антомонов М. Ю. Математическая обработка и анализ медико-биологических данных. 2-е изд. Київ: МІЦ «Медінформ», 2018. 579 с. URL: <https://www.olx.ua/.../antomonov-m-yu-monografya>
2. Перцева Т. О., Гашинова К. Ю., Дмитриченко В. В., Суська К. С. Бронхоектатична хвороба: сучасний стан проблеми та клінічний випадок. *Медичні перспективи*. 2018. Т. 23, № 3(1). С. 153-161. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2018.3\(part1\).142360](https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2018.3(part1).142360)
3. Фещенко Ю. І., Гаврисюк В. К., Дзюблик І. В., Дзюблик О. Я. Інфекційне загострення хронічного обструктивного захворювання легень: місце і роль респіраторних вірусних збудників. *Медичні перспективи*. 2019. Т. 24, № 4. С. 30-35. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2019.4.189191>
4. Antimicrobial peptides and airway bacterial colonization in bronchiectasis/ Vidal OS et al. *Eur Respir J*. 2018. Vol. 53. Suppl. 62. P. OA4948. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.congress-2018.OA4948>
5. British Thoracic Society guideline for bronchiectasis in adults / A. T. Hill et al. *Thorax*. 2019. Vol. 74. S. 1. P. 1-69. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2018-212463>
6. Bronchoarterial ratio in never-smokers adults: implications for bronchial dilation definition/ AA. Diaz et al. *Respirology*. 2017. Vol. 22, No. 1. P. 108-13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/resp.12875>
7. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. CLSI M100 S27:2017. Performance standard for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. 27th edn. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, 2017.

8. A comprehensive approach to lung function in bronchiectasis/ D. Radovanovic et al. *Respir Med*. 2018. Vol. 145. P. 120-129.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2018.10.031>

9. Cornaglia, Giuseppe, René Courcol, Jean-Louis Herrmann. *European Manual of Clinical Microbiology*. 2012. Print.

10. Etiology of non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis in adults and its correlation to disease severity/ S. Lonni et al. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*. 2015. Vol. 12. P. 1764-1770. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201507-472OC>

11. European Respiratory Society guidelines for the management of adult bronchiectasis / E. Polverino et al. *Eur Respir J*. 2017. Vol. 50. P. 1700629. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00629-2017>

12. Geographic variation in the aetiology, epidemiology and microbiology of bronchiectasis/ R. Chandrasekaran et al. *Bmc Pulmonary Medicine*. 2018. Vol. 18, No. 1. P. 14.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-018-0638-0>

13. Matuschek E, Brown DFJ, Kahlmeter G. Development of the EUCAST disk diffusion antimicrobial susceptibility testing method and its implementation in routine microbiology laboratories. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2014. Vol. 20. P. 255-266.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-0691.12373>

14. Microbiome landscape and disease duration role in allergy in adult patients with bronchiectasis/ K Gashynova et al. *Eur Respir J*. 2019. Vol. 54. Suppl. 63. PA2763.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.congress-2019.PA2763>

15. Pneumonic and non-pneumonic exacerbations in bronchiectasis: clinical and microbiological differences / E. Polverino et al. *J Infect*. 2018. No. 77. P. 99-106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2018.04.006>

16. The bronchiectasis severity index. An international derivation and validation study/ JD. Chalmers et al. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2014. No. 189. P. 576-585. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201309-1575OC>

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